

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

IGHOAKPOKRIRE, Alex¹, OKORO, Patience Ewomaoghene²

^{1,2}Delta State University, Abraka Department of Business Education

ABSTRACT: This study examined the relationship among task prioritization, multitasking, work schedule time management technique and job efficiency of Business Education lecturers in Delta State. Six research and hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 144 Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. A sample of 110 lecturers was used for the study. The sampling technique employed in the study was the convenience or accidental sampling technique which is a non-probability sampling technique. The instrument used for this study was a questionnaire titled “Time Management Techniques by Tertiary Institution Lecturers for Job Efficiency Questionnaire (TMTTILJEQ)”. Cronbach’s alpha was utilized in obtaining the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.788, 0.867, 0.745, and 0.747, respectively for the different scales. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Coefficient of Determination was used in answering the research questions while ANOVA associated with linear regression was used in testing the stated hypotheses at an alpha level of 0.05. Based on the analysis, it was revealed that: there was significant relationship between task prioritization techniques, multitasking technique, work schedule technique, and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. It was concluded that task prioritization techniques, multitasking technique, work schedule technique time management techniques were positive predictors of job efficiency. The study recommends that there should be time management workshops for lecturers on the different time management techniques.

KEYWORDS: Job Efficiency, Task Prioritization, Time Management Technique, Multitasking, Work Schedule, Business Education

1 INTRODUCTION

Lecturers at tertiary institutions have a lot of responsibilities. Lecturers must spend their time managing these responsibilities on their own. The ability to comprehend a problem by dissecting it into smaller components, recognizing the main concerns and ramifications, and offering solutions is known as problem solving. Therefore, lecturers must be able to recognize a task or problem and know how to use the appropriate method or strategy to solve it. According to Okoro (2024), people must set aside time to solve the problem or task given the limited amount of time available if they have the necessary skills and techniques to do so and are confident in their ability to handle various kinds of problems in organizations. Any activity, assignment, or project that a person must finish—which typically involves multiple stages—is considered a problem, according to Okoro (2024). Effective and sufficient usage of time management strategies is necessary to address the problems or issues faced by teachers in higher institutions. Individuals' needs, motives, and work-related characteristics all influence how they manage their time. Time is a valuable resource that cannot be bought or preserved. According to Okoro J. (2018), "time management ... scheduling, and prioritizing" is one of a mentor's organizational abilities. As a result, the study found that time is a resource that everyone has access to and that can be used to achieve a lot.

Frederick Winslow Taylor with the works Frank and Lillian Gilbreth are today’s launching fathers of time management which started as a quest to increase productivity and manufacturing based on the skills, effectiveness, efficiency and output of individual workers (Gürbüz & Aydın, 2022). Time management therefore had its beginning with the starting of the industrial revolution and therefore is an expensive ingredient that spice up effective flow of job efficiency and performance in today’s contemporary world (Seneca, 2024). Effective time management entails pursuing endeavors that yield more advantages to people, including those that affect life, the nation, the planet, and the afterlife (Islam et al., 2021). In order to address changing realities and difficulties across organizations, people should develop positive performance in themselves by creating flexible work schedules, keeping an eye on punctuality, assuring procrastination control, and providing time tools and skills (Okoro, P. E. 2018). Individual and organizational performance can be enhanced through the use of proper work schedules, staff education, and effective communication.

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

Since most lecturers and employees nowadays have a lot of tasks to do in a short amount of time, time management is one of the biggest problems they face (Adejo, 2022). Lecturer efficiency results from the proper use of one essential resource, "time," and work efficiency is determined by how time is managed in terms of making enough and complete use of one essential resource, time allocation. Due to inefficient scheduling of the different tasks that need to be completed, job efficiency has significantly decreased organizational performance in the modern day. According to Adejo (2022), time management is a critical component of both individual and corporate performance that requires more focus, and professors at postsecondary institutions are no different. When it comes to achieving tasks and organizational goals, time is of the essence. Ineffective time management is the root cause of many issues that organizations face. Even while time management is vital, companies frequently fail to see it as a necessary survival skill (Adebisi, 2023).

People's ability to make better use of their time and gain control over their affairs is impacted by time management strategies that include goal-setting, prioritization, and stress management, among other things (Fathi & Mourad, 2020). There are a number of time management techniques that have been found to help people, particularly professors in educational institutions who have to finish tasks or meet deadlines. Goal planning is a well-known time management technique that entails establishing specific targets and decomposing them into manageable chunks. According to Locke and Latham (2022), goal-setting enhances motivation and task performance. People can efficiently prioritize their activities and manage their time by establishing clear, quantifiable, realistic, pertinent, and time-bound goals. Another crucial time management technique that enables people to concentrate on and complete high-priority projects on time is task prioritizing. A strategy called time blocking, sometimes referred to as scheduling, is setting aside particular time intervals for various tasks. People can improve their productivity and preserve a worklife balance by developing a regular routine. According to Pešić & Pešić (2019), time blocking helps people set aside specific time for personal pursuits and greatly enhances time management abilities.

Ineffective time management has grown to be a significant problem for the majority of people and businesses nowadays. Lecturers frequently lament the lack of time allotted to complete specified responsibilities, which has led them to work longer hours and occasionally even work when they should be taking care of their personal needs or relaxing. However, in the system of tertiary institutions, poor performance or efficiency has a persistent chokehold. One key strategy for professors and the educational industry to increase efficiency is time management. Given inefficiency or poor time management, particularly when staff members are unable to complete the majority of their duties or schedules due to inadequate time allocation, low organizational efficiency is not a recent phenomenon.

Poor work schedules, tardiness, and job procrastination in the educational system are issues that have deeply ingrained themselves into society. Most businesses are unable to achieve their planned aims and objectives as a result of this cancer, which is becoming more prevalent. Time is the most valuable resource in the universe; it cannot be obtained like money, substituted by man, switched on and off like a machine, or stored like raw materials. The most valuable resource in an organization is time, which we mismanage despite it being an intangible and unique ingredient of production that cannot be recovered once gone. It is discouraging to observe that the majority of lecturers at tertiary institutions, if not all of them, always lament the lack of time to finish academic course work during their busiest semesters. Examining this matter more closely reveals that poor time management is the root cause.

Because time is a unique quantity that a manager cannot store, rent, or buy, it is crucial to plan what can be done in the time that is available rather than considering how much time is available. This means that time management requires the person, the skill, ability, competences, tools, and techniques to manage time. Poor punctuality and procrastination of work are alarming among lecturers, and completion of their routine work is mostly done in a hurry with many errors. Hence, this study examines the relationship among task prioritization, multitasking and scheduling management techniques and job efficiency of Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

2 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between time management techniques and job efficiency of Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- 1) determine the relationship between task prioritization and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State,
- 2) examine the relationship between multitasking and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State,
- 3) assess the relationship between work schedule and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) What is the relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

- 2) What is the relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
- 3) What is the relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

4. HYPOTHESES

- 1) There is no relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State,
- 3) There is no significant relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State,

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Job Efficiency

Efficiency is a complex idea that includes the degree to which predefined goals can be achieved (Pradhan & Jena, 2020) as well as the results of employee actions depending on their knowledge and abilities (Dahkoul, 2018). Efficiency is defined as "something that is done or the products or services produced or provided by a person or group of people" by Rashed and Ahmad (2020). However, it only covers the actions of an employee and excludes the outcomes of those actions.

According to Sendawula et al. (2018), employee efficiency is the result of an individual's work accomplishment following the necessary effort on the job, which is linked to obtaining a meaningful employment, an engaged profile, and sympathetic coworkers or bosses. Furthermore, according to Sendawela et al. (2018), employee efficiency is the capacity of a worker to accomplish a given task as evaluated against predefined criteria of precision, thoroughness, cost, and speed. The ability of individuals or groups to complete tasks, goals, or objectives with the least amount of wasted effort, time, or resources is referred to as employee efficiency. It focuses on how well workers use the resources at their disposal to achieve the intended results.

Concept of Time Management Technique

According to Okoro P. E. (2018a), time is the amount of time—seconds, minutes, hours, or periods—that is anticipated to be needed to finish a specific work in any organization. It is required of employees to make the best use of their time in order to prevent waste. We call this time management. Though many authors have cited and supported the idea that time management is the process of identifying needs, setting goals to meet those needs, prioritizing, and organizing the tasks necessary to accomplish those goals, there is currently no definitive and accurate definition of the term (Lakein, 2023).

According to Okoro P.E. (2018b), time management is a collection of ideas, methods, abilities, resources, and procedures that enable an individual to make the most of his time in order to achieve his goals. In a similar vein, time management is defined by Oliverio et al., as stated in Okoro J. (2018), as organizing and utilizing a workday's hours and minutes in the most effective and efficient way possible to complete the tasks allocated.

According to Onuorah (2020), time management is the process of planning activities or events by first predicting how long a task will take to complete, when it must be finished, and then adjusting any events that could get in the way of finishing it in a timely manner. According to Claessens et al. (2020), time management is the set of behaviors that distinguish individuals who complete tasks on time, adhere to deadlines, and devote little time to their activities from those who frequently arrive late, miss deadlines, devote a lot of time to their activities, and waste time on unimportant things.

Prioritization and Employee Efficiency

When tasks are prioritized, organizational productivity increases. However, it can be challenging to know how to prioritize, especially when faced with urgent duties. Make a list of your tasks and rank them according to importance because, if you want to improve time management and accomplish a lot, an action plan is a useful tool for setting priorities. It will help you distinguish between important tasks, which require better concentration, fewer distractions, and the elimination of tasks that don't add value to the organization (Islam et al., 2021).

If organizational productivity is to be achieved, Onuorah (2020) states that three things must be considered: technical skill, human relation skill, and conceptual skill. If these three items are included in organizational administration, each department will work hard to achieve the goal. As a result, Onuorah (2020) defines human relations as the ability to work with other people amicably. It entails patience, trust, genuine involvement, and interpersonal relationships, which are important at all levels of an organization. Managers should create an environment in which workers work together as a team, with a sense of belonging and dedication, interacting with people, which leads to organizational success.

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

Studies such as Islam et al. (2021) found out that certain time management factors namely prioritization of tasks statistically has a significant positive relationship on job efficiency. Similar to Islam et al. (2021), Onuorah (2020) also revealed in their study that prioritization also had a significant effect on organizational productivity.

Multitasking and Employee Efficiency

Multitasking is the simultaneous execution or quick switching of two or more tasks, usually with the goal of increasing efficiency and productivity (Onuorah, 2020). This concept is highly engrained in our modern work culture, since many individuals are required to manage several duties and deadlines at the same time. The term "multitasking" refers to an individual's ability to work on two or more information-processing tasks simultaneously or concurrently (Rekart, 2021). As a result, the individual can execute various things that all need cognitive, such as reading email or conversing online while attending a meeting or working with a group. The underlying need for multitasking at work is that the individual must manage multiple subtasks simultaneously for a limited amount of time.

Many researchers have noted that multitasking may not be as successful as time management, as generally believed. One study looked at how students perform in school with work for time sharing and work for multitasking: "This means that dividing attention by multitasking impedes learning and performance in the short-term and may, be underutilizing brain structures necessary for the correct type of learning, affect long-term memory and retention" (Rekart, 2021, p.1). In another study, Adeyefa et al. (2024) discovered that, there was significant relationship of time management techniques on employee productivity (EP) in Ondo State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) in Ondo State. Njagi and Malel (2022) indicated a direct relationship between work performance and the effective management of available time. It was found that task splitting will be more frequently preferred to assigning all tasks to one agent (Schottner, 2022.). This occurs because as detailed above, a person only has a certain capacity for tasks.

Influence of Work Scheduling Technique on Employee Efficiency

Kandie and Chepkilot (2022) describe a work schedule as the time when an employee is expected to be present and working. In many circumstances, the employer will establish the number of days and hours worked. An employee's work schedule contains the times and days that they are expected to be on the job.

According to Kandie and Chepkilot (2022), when an employer hires to fill a vacancy, the organization determines the employment work schedule. Many employers set a schedule for their personnel. The timetable can be created with fixed hours, so the employee knows exactly when they will be working each week. Other organisations may have a more flexible scheduling approach. Employers use this to provide employees the flexibility to change their arrival and leave times, as well as choosing their work days. The scheduling process can be done the oldfashioned way, with a corporation manually determining the work plan for its personnel on paper or via a computer spreadsheet or calendar.

Several studies have related employee efficiency to time management methods, including work schedules used by organizations. A work schedule is the number of hours per day and days per week that an employee is required to work (Kandie & Chepkilot, 2022). Nyamka and Ndang (2021) revealed in their study that work schedule had a positive influence on employee performance. Kandie and Chepkilot (2022) examining the effect of work scheduling on employee efficiency confirmed a strong statistically significant positive relationship between work scheduling and employee performance in selected private hospitals in Uasin-Gishu County, Kenya. This means that scheduling of tasks helps in the proper management of time necessary for conducting of tasks significantly influence employees' performance.

6. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: The Pickle Jar Theory

This study's theoretical framework is based on Jeremy Wright's (2002) Pickle Jar Theory, which Gunawan (2024) has embraced. This theory proposes a way for prioritizing tasks by comparing time management to a container full of diverse items: stones represent key chores, gravel represent important but delegable tasks, and sand represents less critical activities. By prioritizing well, one can handle the most important tasks first, potentially increasing productivity. According to Gunawan (2024), this method helps avoid the dangers of multitasking, which can cause feelings of overwhelm and decreased effectiveness. Effective time management maximizes energy and focus. The Pickle Jar Theory enables people to evaluate the relevance and urgency of activities based on characteristics such as duration and impact, which helps them balance multiple duties within a limited time frame (Idowu & Bamire, 2022).

7. METHODOLOGY

The study used a correlational survey research approach. In this type of study, the researcher must present questionnaires to obtain respondents' opinions, attitudes, or impressions. The survey included 144 Business Education lecturers from Delta State's tertiary schools. The study used the purposive sampling method, which employs the accidental or convenience sampling strategy. The researcher used respondents who were either available or willing to engage in the survey. Based on this, a sample of 110 lecturers was selected. The study employed a closed-ended questionnaire with 60 items arranged on a four-point scale.

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

The questionnaire had four scales vis-à-vis Job Efficiency Scale, Task Prioritization Scale, Multitasking Technique Scale and Work Schedule Technique Scale. Each of the scale contained 15 items which were personally developed by the researcher. Cronbach’s alpha was utilized in obtaining the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.788, 0.867, 0.745, and 0.747, respectively for the different scales. These results showed a high level of reliability, demonstrating appropriateness, making the instrument suitable for the study. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Coefficient of Determination was used in answering the research questions while ANOVA associated with linear regression was used in testing the stated hypotheses at an alpha level of 0.05 significance.

8. DATA ANALYSIS RESEARCH QUESTION ONE

What is the relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 1: Pearson correlation coefficient and coefficient of determination of task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Task Prioritization Technique	110	43.85	3.771	.659	.434	43.4%	High Positive Relationship
Job Efficiency	110	44.20	3.485				

In Table 1, the analysis shows a Pearson-r value of 0.659 indicating that there is high positive relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The r² value of 0.434 is the coefficient of determination and this implies that the amount of contribution of task prioritization technique to job efficiency is 43.4%.

Research Question Two

What is the relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation and coefficient of determination of the relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Multitasking Technique	110	42.86	4.538	0.559	0.312	31.2	Moderate Positive Relationship
Job Efficiency	110	44.20	3.485				

Table 2 shows a Pearson-r value of 0.559 which indicates a moderate positive relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The r² value of 0.312 indicates the coefficient of determination and the amount of contribution of multitasking technique to job efficiency which is 31.2%.

Research Question Three

What is the relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 3: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination on the relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Work Schedule Technique	110	42.35	4.594	.525 ^a	.276	27.6	Moderate Positive Relationship
Job Efficiency	110	44.20	3.485				

Table 3 shows a Pearson-r value of 0.525 which indicates a moderate positive relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The r² value of 0.273 is the coefficient of determination, hence, the amount of contribution of work schedule technique to job efficiency is 27.3%.

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

9. Testing of Hypotheses Hypothesis 1:

There is no relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4: Regression analysis on relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

ANOVA					
Model	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Regression	4.595	1	4.595	.376	.001 ^b
Residual	1319.005	108	12.213		
Total	1323.600	109			
Variables in the Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Ratio	P
(Constant)	41.813	3.906		10.706	.000
TASK PRIORITIZATION TECHNIQUE	.054	.089	.659	.613	.001

a. Dependent Variable: JOB EFFICIENCY **^b Significance: $P \leq 0.05$**

The result in Table 4 shows the F-calculated value of .376 and a p-value of 0.001. Testing at an alpha level of 0.05, the P-value is less than the alpha level, hence, the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is significant relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The unstandardized coefficient (B-value) of .054 shows that task prioritization technique is good at predicting job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions. The standardized coefficient value [$\beta = 0.659$; $P < 0.05$] indicates that task prioritization technique is significant at predicting job efficiency.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Table 5: Regression analysis on the relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

ANOVA					
Model	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Regression	4.634	1	4.634	.379	.009 ^b
Residual	1318.966	108	12.213		
Total	1323.600	109			
Variables in the Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Ratio	P
(Constant)	42.252	3.179		13.291	.000
MULTITASKING TECHNIQUE	.045	.074	.559	.616	.009

a. Dependent Variable: JOB EFFICIENCY **^b Significance: $P \leq 0.05$**

The result in Table 5 shows the relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State is significant. The table indicates the F-value of 0.379 and P-value of 0.009. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the P-value of 0.009 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This shows that there is significant relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The unstandardized coefficient (B-value) of 0.045 ($P = 0.009 < 0.05$) indicates that multitasking technique is moderately positively significant at predicting business education lecturers job efficiency. The standardized coefficient value [$\beta = 0.559$; $P < 0.05$] indicates that multitasking technique is significant at predicting business education lecturers job efficiency at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 6: Regression analysis on the relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State

ANOVA					
Model 1	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Regression	.819	1	.819	.067	.006 ^b
Residual	1322.781	108	12.248		
Total	1323.600	109			

Variables in the Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Ratio	P
(Constant)	43.401	3.107		13.967	.000
Work Schedule Technique	.019	.073	.525	.259	.006

a. Dependent Variable: JOB EFFICIENCY

The result in Table 6 shows the relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The table shows the F-calculated value of .067 and a P-value of 0.006. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the P-value of 0.006 is less than the alpha level of 0.05 therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. This revealed that there is significant relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

The unstandardized coefficient (B-value) of .019 shows that work schedule technique is good at predicting business education lecturers’ job efficiency in tertiary institutions. The standardized coefficient value [$\beta = 0.525$; $P < 0.05$] indicates that work schedule technique is significant at predicting job efficiency. This implies that 52.5% of the changes in job efficiency is explained by work schedule technique and 47.5% were other factors.

10. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analysis in Table 1 which answered the second research question revealed that existence of a strong positive relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This analysis indicates that the change in job efficiency among Business Education lecturers in Delta State Higher Institutions was attributed to task prioritization. Further testing of hypothesis, as shown in Table 4 revealed that there was relationship between task prioritization technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Hence, task prioritization technique was good at predicting the job efficiency of business education lecturers. This finding is in line with Islam et al. (2021) who found out that certain time management factors namely prioritization of tasks statistically has a significant positive relationship on job efficiency. Similar to Islam et al. (2021), Onuorah (2020) revealed their study that prioritization also had a significant effect on organizational productivity.

The analysis, as indicated in Table 2, providing answer to research question three revealed a moderate positive relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency. Further testing of hypothesis in relation to the third research question of the study, as shown in Table 5, revealed that there was significant relationship between multitasking technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

The analysis portrayed that multitasking technique was moderately significant at predicting business education lecturers’ job efficiency in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Onuorah (2020) corroborates the above finding. In line with the above finding Onuorah (2020) revealed that multitasking has a significant effect on organizational productivity.

The analysis, as shown in Table 3, providing answer to research question three revealed the existence of a moderate positive relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Further analysis of the hypothesis as indicated in Table 6 revealed that there was significant relationship between work schedule technique and the job efficiency of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This implies that work schedule technique was significant at predicting job efficiency. This finding aligns with Nyamka and Ndong (2021) who pointed out that work schedule had a positive influence on employee performance. This means that scheduling of tasks helps in the proper management of time necessary for conducting of tasks significantly influence employees’ performance. Kandie and Chepkilot

Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

(2022) examining the effect of work scheduling on employee efficiency confirmed a strong statistically significant positive relationship between work scheduling and employee performance.

11. CONCLUSION

The study highlights the critical importance of effective time management strategies for improving job efficiency among Business Education lecturers in Delta State. Key findings include that task prioritization is a strong predictor of job efficiency, multitasking techniques positively correlate with higher productivity, and structured work scheduling is essential for efficient practices. In summary, combining task prioritization, effective multitasking, and systematic scheduling can significantly enhance lecturer performance. These insights suggest that educational administrators should provide training in these areas to improve outcomes. Future research could further examine the application of these techniques across different educational settings.

12. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations have been made based on the findings and conclusions from the study.

1. The study recommends that lecturers should employ different time management techniques that best suit them for the completion of tasks. Laying emphasis on the importance of good time management is a great way of ensuring that all employees are all aware of importance of time management.
2. Lecturers should adopt the task prioritization technique in order to carry out their duties effectively. It is recommended that lecturers should adopt prioritization time management strategies by drawing up a to-dolist in order of priority and delegate some responsibilities, if necessary to their colleagues, this will enable them to work in line with Wright's pickle jar theory; ensuring that lecturers prioritize their tasks and improve their performance.
3. The study recommends that there should be time management workshops for lecturers on the different time management techniques in their execution of their tasks in order for them to be aware of their importance and know exactly how to execute the techniques. It is important that teachers know that the more they know how to effectively manage time, the more they can be able to be efficient in their jobs.

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Relationship Among Task Prioritization, Multitasking, Work Schedule Time Management Technique and Job Efficiency of Business Education Lecturers in Delta State

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